

Utilisation of Paediatric Electroencephalogram at Komfo Anokye Teaching Hospital

Charles K. Hammond,^{1,2*} Angela Osei-Bonsu,¹ Michael Acheampong,¹ Leticia Sam-Onumah,¹ Perpetual Kanzie,¹ Patience Kwawu,¹ Joslin A. Dogbe,^{1,2} Sam Dzodzomenyo,³

1. Paediatric Neurology Unit, Child Health Directorate, Komfo Anokye Teaching Hospital, Kumasi.

2. Department of Child Health, School of Medicine and Dentistry, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Kumasi, Ghana.

3. Division of Paediatric Neurology and Sleep Medicine, Dayton Children's Hospital, Dayton OH, USA.

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*Corresponding author: Dr Charles Hammond, Department of Child Health, School of Medicine and Dentistry, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Kumasi, Ghana. Email: ckhammond@knust.edu.gh

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ABSTRACT

Background: Though the diagnosis of epilepsy remains clinical, the electroencephalogram (EEG) is important in further evaluation of the patient, providing details on seizure type(s) and sometimes confirming an epilepsy syndrome. In Ghana, until 2016, EEG service was only available in the capital, Accra, and not accessible to many patients with epilepsy. Following the introduction of paediatric EEG service at the Komfo Anokye Teaching Hospital (KATH) in 2016, many children with epilepsy are referred from various parts of the country for further evaluation. There is no data on where these children are referred from, who is referring them, and how long it takes to get the EEG done and receive a report. **Objective:** The study aimed to determine the characteristics of referrals of children seeking EEG service at KATH. **Methods:** A retrospective review of EEG referral letters and reports of patients who had EEG recordings at the Paediatric EEG laboratory from January to December 2020 was done to determine the age, sex, referring facility, region, waiting times, and the abnormalities reported. For patients referred from outside KATH, the distance from the referring centers to KATH was estimated using Google Maps. The data was entered and analyzed using Microsoft Excel. **Results:** Two hundred and fifty-six patients including 57.8% males and 42.2% females, 98.4% children and adolescents and 1.6% adults, with age range 1-492 months (median = 60 months, IQR 21-106) had EEGs done in the laboratory in 2020. They were referred from 10 out of the 16 regions in Ghana, with Ashanti contributing the majority (74%). Most were referred by general practitioners/family physicians (49.2%) paediatricians (18.4%) and paediatric neurologists (16.8%). For referrals coming from outside KATH, the mean distance from the referring centres to KATH was 55.1km (IQR 5.3-107.0km). After requesting an EEG, it took a median duration of 4 days (IQR 1-9) to get the recording done, and a further median duration of 20 days (IQR 8-34) to receive a report. Fifty-seven percent of the EEGs were reported as abnormal. EEG abnormalities were most common in patients referred with seizures (not specified) (38.7%), followed by generalized (32.8%) and focal (14.1%) seizures. **Conclusion:** EEG referrals to the laboratory were commonest among general practitioners and paediatricians. Patients were mostly school age children. There were significant waiting times from the times of referrals to final reports. To improve access and reduce waiting times, efforts should be made to establish additional laboratories in other tertiary centres and train more experts.

Key words: Electroencephalogram, Epilepsy, Children, Referrals, Ghana.

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